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“The Number 13”

They said the number 13 is an unlucky number. But on October 13, it was the long word of our vows. It had been sewn into the simple words of the "I do" that we exchanged that day. On that day, the world seemed to be still for a moment, as if waiting for the way for the love we were making. No great noise, no extravagant scene-round two certain, steady hearts want only to walk together.

Thirteen meant far less than a number now; it was the foundation of our forever. And every year, every time there is an "I love you" whisper: luck was never found in superstition; it always existed in you.